

DIGITAL MODELING OF GRAVITY ANOMALIES

*Isgandarov E.,**Associate professor,**Department of "Geophysics" Azerbaijan State Oil and Industrial University (ASOIU), Azerbaijan, Baku**Jabizadeh L.**Master student,**Department of "Geophysics" Azerbaijan State Oil and Industrial University (ASOIU), Azerbaijan, Baku***Abstract**

The article is devoted to digital modeling of gravity anomalies, the solution of which plays an important role in the geological interpretation of the observed anomalies in gravity prospecting. The object of study is the Zardab uplift, in the section of which Mesozoic volcanic-sedimentary deposits take part, which are well displayed in a gravity field. Using modern graphical tools such as SURFER and the software developed at the Department of Geophysics for processing and interpreting gravimetric anomalies, 2D and 3D maps of the surface of Mesozoic deposits, maps of the local gravity field and the gravitational influence of the Zardab area were calculated and built, which gives the most complete spatial and areal representation of nature gravity anomalies.

Keywords: modeling, structural model, gravity model, digital modeling, local gravity anomaly.

Introduction

In prospecting, exploration and study of the geological structure of prospective oil and gas and ore-bearing areas, the gravity method of exploration is of great importance, which is based on studying the nature of the distribution of gravity fields created by individual structural uplifts, which have density properties of its constituent rocks. At the stage of quantitative interpretation of gravity data, a very important task is solved - modeling of gravity anomalies, which is of great importance in geological interpretation [1-11]. Currently, this problem is being solved using modern graphic programs in two-dimensional and three-dimensional versions based on the results of computer calculations of theoretical gravity fields according to the developed algorithms and programs, which provides the most complete idea of the shape, depth and size of the desired geological objects. This explains the relevance of ongoing research in this area. The purpose of this study is the digital modeling of local gravity anomalies and the assessment of the gravitational influence of the Zardab structure, located in the eastern part of the Middle Kura depression of Azerbaijan and promising for oil and gas.

Means and methods

Real geological objects that create gravitational anomalies can only be likened to regular-shaped bodies only approximately, and therefore the calculated parameters of geological objects in most cases give only the most general idea of their actual sizes. You can refine the parameters of the object by choosing a body whose anomaly coincides with the observed one. By successively changing the shape of the body, one can achieve a close correspondence between the observed

and calculated curves. The coincidence of these curves allows us to state that the resulting body configuration corresponds to the shape of a real geological object. All methods are based on the replacement of the gravity action of such a body by the action of the sum of bodies of the simplest form, the effect of which can be accurately calculated. With their help, a body of arbitrary shape can easily be divided into elementary figures of the same shape, the gravitational action of which can be accurately calculated using formulas. In this case, the gravity effect of a body of arbitrary shape is equal to the total effect of all elementary figures contained in the volume of the body. ASOIU has developed GTEOR3D FORCE-FORTRAN program at the Department of Geophysics, which allow calculating the vertical component of the gravity field from a geological body of arbitrary shape based on the division of the body into elementary prisms [1-7]. Digital modeling of gravity anomalies is currently widely used, as it allows in two-dimensional and three-dimensional versions to more accurately and visually present the geophysical results obtained at the interpretation stage. To implement digital modeling, graphic programs such as SURFER and others are used, which allow you to digitize the results and perform various transformations in order to filter useful information [11].

At the beginning, the GTEOR3D program was tested on the example of a model structure (Fig. 1). The structure is represented by depth isolines in kilometers with a cross section of 0.02 km and is slightly elongated to the north. To estimate the gravitational influence in a three-dimensional version, the structural map was quantized with a square grid with a step of 1 km.

VZ VALUES BY AREA, MGAL

0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.3
0.2	0.3	0.6	0.9	1.0	0.8	0.5
0.3	0.5	1.1	1.9	2.3	1.7	0.9
0.3	0.7	1.5	2.9	3.5	2.5	1.2
0.3	0.7	1.7	3.2	4.0	2.8	1.3
0.3	0.6	1.4	2.6	3.2	2.3	1.1
0.3	0.5	1.0	1.7	2.0	1.5	0.8
0.2	0.3	0.6	0.8	0.9	0.7	0.5

Fig. 2. Initial data and results of computer calculation of Vz

Fig.3. Field Vz of the structure model (in units of mGal)

method). Analysis and generalization of gravimetric data were carried out in the field in the 1970s, after that high-precision field research works were carried out in the 1980s (Fig. 4). In 1970 year, preparatory works for drilling the structure began. Well was dug to a depth of 4608 meters in the arch part of the structure in 1972. Later, another well was dug to 2.5 km west of that well. Technically point, this well could not be fully reached to the project depth. Other well, dug to a depth about 4825 meters, revealed carbonate sediments of the Upper Cretaceous and confirmed the data of seismic prospecting. Thus, oil manifestations were noted in Eocene-Upper Cretaceous sediments in these wells. Although short-term oil flow was obtained in the search well, dug in the Zardab field with a production about

350 tons per day, the well was not tested in normal condition later due to strong waterlogging. Volcanogenic-sedimentary deposits of the Mesozoic, which have excessive density (about 0.2g/sm^3 , take part in the section of the Zardab uplift. It should be noted that the Zardab uplift was first register on the maps of local gravity anomalies received from gravity survey data. Digital modeling of the Zardab structure itself was performed. To do this, using the SURFER program in the Digit mode, the values of depth of the structural map the Zardab area were digitized. Then, based on the grid received in the mapping mode, the structural map itself was built in 2D and 3D versions, on which the modern interface displays a structural map of the Zardab uplift. The amplitude this uplift reaches approximately 500m (Fig.5-6).

Fig. 4. Structural map of Upper Cretaceous deposits according to data seismic surveys (in units of meters) [9].

Fig.5. Structural 2D map over the surface of the Upper Cretaceous deposits of the Zardab-Shikhabagi area (in units of meters, according to the results of digital modeling)

Fig.6. Structural 3D map over the surface of the Upper Cretaceous deposits of the Zardab-Shikhabagi area (in units of meters, according to the results of digital modeling)

Models of gravity and magnetic fields along a two-dimensional profile crossing the Zardab Rise were calculated using the GMTEOR FORTRAN program (Fig. 7). According to these results, the corresponding V_z and Z curves were constructed in the EXCEL program. As can be seen from the figure, the calculated field is characterized by two gravitational and magnetic

maxima. The amplitude of the gravity curve is equal to 2.2 mGal.

On the Zardab area in the eastern part of the Middle Kur depression, the observed gravitational field was transformed at the Department of Geophysics by the averaging method with a radius of 10 km, on which the local Zardab anomaly was identified. Below the results

of digital modeling of this local anomaly in two and three dimensions are shown (Fig. 8-9), as well as a comparative composition of these two variants (Fig. 10). As can be seen, the intensity of the local Zardab anomaly reaches 2 mGal.

The GTEOR3D program was used to estimate the gravitational influence of the Zardab uplift over the area. For this, initial data were prepared based on uniform quantization of the depth values of the structural map on a square grid (Fig. 11).

Fig.7. Calculated Δg and Z curves (Zardab area)

Fig.8. Δg_{10} gravitational local anomaly of Zardab area 2D representation of the map

Fig.9. Δg_{10} gravitational local anomaly of Zardab area 3D representation of the map

Fig.10. Δg_{10} gravitational local anomaly of the Zardab area in 2D and 3D comparative form

DIMENSIONS OF THE QUANTIZATION STRUCTURE, OBSERVATION AREAS AND EXCESS DENSITY

7 7 0.20000
 0.00000 28.00000 0.00000 28.00000 4.00000
 4.00000 4.00000 4.00000

UPPER DEPTHS

4.50000 4.45000 4.44000 4.30000 4.20000 4.10000 4.10000
 4.59000 4.52000 4.40000 4.40000 4.30000 4.25000 4.20000
 4.70000 4.59000 4.40000 4.38000 4.40000 4.34000 4.23000
 4.82000 4.70000 4.55000 4.40000 4.30000 4.22000 4.23000
 4.95000 4.80000 4.65000 4.45000 4.18000 4.18000 4.30000
 5.03000 4.86000 4.65000 4.45000 4.30000 4.35000 4.30000
 5.10000 4.90000 4.70000 4.60000 4.58000 4.59000 4.35000

LOWER DEPTHS

5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000
 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000
 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000
 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000
 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000
 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000
 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000 5.20000

VZ VALUES BY AREA

0.4 0.6 0.9 1.1 1.2 1.3 1.3
 0.6 1.2 1.9 2.3 2.6 2.8 2.9
 0.8 1.7 2.8 3.4 3.9 4.2 4.4
 0.8 1.8 3.0 3.8 4.3 4.7 4.8
 0.8 1.7 2.7 3.6 4.3 4.8 4.9
 0.7 1.4 2.4 3.2 4.1 4.7 5.0
 0.6 1.2 2.0 2.8 3.7 4.3 4.6
 0.5 0.9 1.5 2.3 3.0 3.5 3.6

Fig. 11. Initial data and results of computer calculation V_z of the Zardab uplift

It should be noted that the program calculates the values of the gravitational field based on the division of the structure into elementary volumetric prisms. Then, based on the calculated gravity values, a 2D and 3D V_z map was constructed (Fig. 12-13). As you can see, the Zardab and Shikhbagi structures are displayed in the

same maximum. This is explained by the fact that the amplitude of the Shikhbagi uplift is greater than the amplitude of Zardab on the one hand, and on the other hand, the step of splitting the structure and the observed points (computation points) is too large (4 km).

Fig. 12. Calculated field V_z Zardab-Shikhabagi (2D, in units mGals)

Fig. 13. Calculated field V_z Zardab-Shikhabagi (3D, in units mGals)

Conclusions:

1. A review and analysis of the issues of digital modeling of gravity anomalies and geological structures based on geophysical survey data has been completed. The importance and effectiveness of the use of digital modeling for solving the main geological problem of gravity exploration is shown.

2. The FORCE-FORTRAN GTEOR3D developed at the Department of Geophysics was tested on the example of a model structure, which showed the effectiveness of this program for digital modeling.

3. The structural map of the Zardab-Shikhabagi uplift, which was built on a computer in 2D and 3D versions, on which the Zardab uplift is distinguished with an amplitude of about 0.5 km, and the Shikhabagi uplift is characterized by an amplitude of 0.8 km.

4. The gravitational effect which was calculated in a two-dimensional version using the GMTEOR FORTRAN- program developed at the Department of Geophysics of ASOIU along the profile crossing the Zardab structure, and the curves of gravity and magnetic field were analyzed.

5. The local gravity anomaly Δg_{10} of the Zardab uplift obtained at the department was digitized and a digital model of this gravity anomaly was built using a modern interface in 2D and 3D versions, on which the

Zardab local maximum of the gravity field with an intensity of 2 mGal is more clearly distinguished.

6. The gravitational influence of the Zardab-Shikhabagi uplift in the section of which Mesozoic volcanogenic-sedimentary deposits are involved was estimated according to the GTEOR3D program with an excess density of 0.2 g/cm³. The Zardab-Shikhabagi uplift, which is promising in terms of oil and gas, is well displayed in a gravity field with an intensity of approximately 5 mGal.

References

1. Amiraslanov T.S. An algorithm for calculating theoretical gravitational effects on local folds located on the slopes of large geological structures. Oil and gas. No. 5, 1979, p.7-12. (in Russian).
2. Iskandarov E.H. Evaluation of the gravitational influences of the Mesozoic structures of the eastern part of the Middle- Kur basin in a three-dimensional version on the computer. Tesisy of Dokl. VII Rep. scientific-conf. Postgraduate students of Az-na universities, Baku, 1984, vol. I, p.232. (in Russian).
3. Iskandarov E.H. Evaluation of the gravitational influence of the structures of complex regions. Subject. Sat. scientific articles Geof. Research Oil and gas, AGNA, Baku, 1991, p.97-101. (in Russian).

4. Iskandarov E.H. Estimation of the gravitational influence of oil deposits at various depths. *Journal Geologist of Azerbaijan, Scientific Bulletin of the Society of Petroleum Geologists of Azerbaijan*, No. 10, Baku, 2005, pp. 85-88 (in Russian).
5. Iskandarov E.H. Algorithm for estimating the gravitational effects of structures of arbitrary shape. The material of the scientific conference dedicated to the 100th anniversary of Academician H.A. Ahmadov's birth, Baku- 2006 p. 35-36 (in Russian).
6. Iskandarov E.H. Estimation of RTA (Reservoir Type Anomalies) associated with the zones of decompression of rocks. *Journal Geologist of Azerbaijan, Scientific Bulletin of the Society of Petroleum Geologists of Azerbaijan*, No. 15, Baku, 2011, pp. 96-101 (in Russian).
7. İsgandarov E.H. Digital modeling of the gravity field of the Muradkhanly uplift. *Australian Journal of Education and Science*. Avstraliya. Sidney university. 2018, 9 p.
8. İsgandarov E., Seyidov V. Digital modeling of analytical continuation of gravitational field. *German International Journal of Modern Science, EARTH SCIENCES*, № 29, 2022, pp.11-14. ISSN 2701-8377.
9. Korchagin I.M., Yakymchuk N.A., Micheeva T.L. et al. Gravity and magnetic modeling of anomalous sources with complex configuration. *Geophysics in the Baltic region // Problems and prospects for the new millennium (Int. conf., Sept. 26–30, 2000)*. Tallinn, Estonia, 2000. P. 83–84.
10. Salmanov A.M., Yusifov K.M. On the prospects for oil and gas potential of the northeastern side of the Yevlakh-Agdzhabedy trough. *Journal «SOCAR Proceedings»*, No. 2, Baku, 2013, pp. 6- (in Russian).
11. Silkin. K.Yu. Geoinformation system Golden Software Surfer 8. Teaching aid for universities. Publishing and Printing Center of Voronezh State University, Surfer.pdf, 2008, p.66 (in Russian).